

My computer is infected: the role of users' sensation seeking and domain-specific risk perceptions and risk attitudes on computer harm

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Final version 26 January 2016

Literature has traditionally shown the potentially harmful consequences of risk-taking in a variety of domains. Less scholarly attention, however, has been directed to the study of risk-taking in the computer use domain. Using scanned data from 1902 computers, we sought to analyze the potentially harmful consequences that sensation-seeking and computer use risk perceptions and attitudes had on users' computer vulnerability. Results of the study indicated that general sensation-seeking as well as computer use risk perceptions and risk attitudes were predictive of computer harm. The general measure of sensation-seeking was predictive of both risk perceptions and risk attitudes which in turn translated into the existence of malicious software in users' computers.

Keywords: sensation-seeking; domain-specific risk; risk perceptions; risk attitudes

Introduction

The idea that the end-user is one of the key factors in cyber security is not new (Anderson and Agarwal 2010; Arachchilage and Love 2013; Davinson and Sillence 2010; Workman, Bommer, and Straub 2008) and although numerous technical, governmental, and legal experts are continuing to warn about the danger of computer and Internet use, some individuals still do not follow online and computer basic safety standards. They still put themselves and their equipment at risk by opening unexpected email attachments, downloading malware, using weak or compromised passwords, clicking inside pop-ups, clicking on links in emails (Leder, Werner, and Martini 2009; Workman, Bommer, and Straub 2008), or posting online personal information that may be used maliciously by third parties (Shillair et al. 2015). These practices may compromise not only the security of their computers but also their personal safety due to potential cyber victimization.

Hackers and cyber criminals are aware of this situation and routinely use social engineering tactics to trick users into installing malicious software (malware) or otherwise obviate technical security controls (Abraham and Chengalur-Smith 2010). Given this reality, we need to understand why individuals will assume greater levels of risk when interacting with computers (computer risk-taking).

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The literature on risk-taking has provided several theoretical explanations to researchers on the nature of risk-taking. Broadly speaking, both the situation in which the risk behavior is enacted (or omitted) as well as the characteristics of the person who engages in risk behaviors have been used to explain risk-taking.

On the one hand, mainstream theories of health and safety behaviors indicate that the perception of a behavior as risky might be a key aspect that allows to understand why people do not initiate unhealthy or unsafe behaviors (Janz and Becker 1984; Knuth et al. 2014; Rippetoe and Rogers 1987; Schwarzer 2008; Weinstein 1993). Available empirical evidence seems to support this claim (see reviews in Harrison, Mullen, and Green 1992; van der Pligt, van Schie, and Hoevenagel 1998). Relatedly, decision-making theories have pointed out how cost-benefit analyses could be used to explain risk behaviors. From this perspective, people would behave in a risky way if they perceive there would be some gain after a cost-benefit type analysis (Bechara 2004). Thus, risk perceptions have been linked to the people's beliefs that some pleasure would be achieved or, alternatively, some negative outcome would be avoided if a behavior is enacted or omitted (Ersche et al. 2005). An important characteristic of this approach is that risk perceptions and behaviors are conceptualized as domain specific: an individual might exhibit risk-taking tendencies in one domain (e.g. financial) but display more conservative behaviors in another (e.g. computer use). In line with these arguments, Weber and her colleagues have argued that risk-taking would be a function of the perceived risk, its expected benefits, and the attitude toward risk (Weber 2001; Weber and Milliman 1997). Perceptions of risk and risk-taking behaviors have been shown to vary by content domain, including health risks (Gerrard et al. 1996), adventurous sports (Llewellyn 2008), entrepreneurship (Mitchell et al. 2002), and risky driving (Hammond and Horswill 2001).

On the other hand, risk-taking propensity has been used to explain why some individuals are likely to favor risky decisions and engage in risky activities. Since the late 1970s, research has shown that there is a link between risk-taking and personality and that risk propensity could be more a characteristic of an individual than their situation (see Nicholson et al. 2005; for an analysis). Research on stable personality traits of risk-takers (Bromiley and Curley 1992; Chraif et al. 2015; Cummings, Berube, and Lavelle 2013; Lejuez et al. 2002; Nicholson et al. 2005) has suggested that risk-takers do not seem to present psychological or social adjustment problems. Rather, they would present a personality factor characterized by one's need for novel, varied, and complex experiences (Zuckerman 1979): sensation-seeking. Available empirical evidence suggest that sensation-seeking might be a highly consistent predictor of various kinds of risk-taking including sports that involve physical risks (Zuckerman 1983), gambling (Anderson and Brown 1984), risky sex behaviors (Zuckerman, Tushup, and Finner 1976), and other risky activities (Zuckerman 1974; Zuckerman and Kuhlman 2000). An important feature of this approach is that risk-taking would be relatively consistent across domains rather than domain specific which would potentially contradict predictions of, for instance, decision-making theories.

Weber and Milliman (1997) (see also Weber, Blais, and Betz 2002) have shown that the above does not necessarily represent an inconsistency. These authors have empirically found that while the degree of risk perceived in a situation can vary according to the characteristics of the situation and could be regarded as domain specific, the attitude to perceive risk (the degree to which people find perceived risk

attractive) remains stable across situations. Data from perceived risk attitude studies, such as Weber, Blais, and Betz (2002), suggest that both general (e.g. sensation-seeking) and domain-specific (e.g. perceived risk) risk propensities are possible (see also, Cheung, Wu, and Tao 2014). In this framework, it is suggested that the two key inputs to risk-taking are risk perception (which would be domain specific) and risk propensity (which would be rather stable).

While there is an extensive research effort to understand the key aspects of risk-taking and its connections to personality traits and domain-specific aspects, less scholarly attention has been directed to the specific study of risk-taking in the computer use domain. It is unclear whether sensation- and non-sensation-seekers use computers and Internet for different reasons, although computer and Internet use might provide a novel environment where users with greater levels of sensation-seeking are likely to be fascinated by the Internet and suffer the adverse effects of its use. Recent research suggests that sensation-seekers might probably use computers in a different way than non-sensation-seekers (Chen et al. 2011; McKibbin, Fridsma, and Crowley 2007). Thus, sensation-seeking might be predictive of insecure computing behaviors and problematic Internet use (Shi, Chen, and Tian 2011; Vance et al. 2014). For instance, the general propensity to risk (sensation-seeking) was found to be predictive of a tendency to open risky emails (Chen et al. 2011) and also was related to computer-mediated searching processes and techniques (McKibbin, Fridsma, and Crowley 2007). The empirical evidence linking domain-specific (computer and Internet use) risk propensities and computer risky behavior, however, is almost nonexistent. In this sense, while more general measures of general propensity to risk are available (see Harrison et al. 2005 for a review), to our knowledge, no available computer use-specific measures have been provided to researchers. Instruments such as the Domain-Specific Risk Taking Scale (Weber, Blais, and Betz 2002) measure risk-accepting attitudes in various domains (e.g. financial, health, ethical, social, and recreational risk) with no reference to computer use. Given that domain specific is an important feature of theories of risk-taking, the lack of available computer use domain-specific measurement instruments has become an important limitation to the development of the field.

In the present study, we seek to analyze the potentially harmful consequences that both computer users' general propensity to risk and computer users' risk perceptions and attitudes might have on their equipment. We take advantage of a large national data-set of computer users whose equipment was scanned in search of malicious software. Scanning results were analyzed in light of the users' propensity to risk (i.e. sensation-seeking) and their domain-specific computer risk perceptions and risk attitudes. The objectives of the study were twofold. On the one hand, reliable computer use domain-specific measures of risk perceptions and risk attitudes were developed. On the other hand, the influence of both sensation-seeking and domain-specific risk perceptions and risk attitudes on computers' harm was analyzed. Given the empirical relationships found in the literature among socio-demographic variables and both sensation-seeking and risk perceptions and attitudes, the former were controlled for (Byrnes, Miller, and Schafer 1999; Martin and Leary 2001; Nicholson et al. 2005; Powell and Ansic 1997; Slovic et al. 2004; Sund, Svensson, & Andersson, *forthcoming*; Ungemack 1994).

Methods

Participants

We used data from the Cybersecurity and Confidence in Spanish Households national survey conducted in June 2014 by the National Observatory of Telecommu-

nications and Information Society of the Spanish Ministry of Industry. The survey was designed to measure cyber security in digitalized Spanish households. Two types of data were used in the survey: reported and scanned data. Reported data referred to the responses that participants gave to the online questionnaire. Scanned data were obtained from scanning of equipment (computers) upon approval of participants. Personal equipment was scanned with iScan software, which analyzed the presence of malware through the use of 50 antivirus engines. The iScan software was remotely installed in participants' computers to regularly search for resident malware and to collect data about the operative system, their up-to-date status, and the presence of installed security tools.

Participants belonged to a representative sample of the Spanish population of Internet users. Primary sampling units were households and secondary sampling units were individuals within households. First, a Spanish representative sample of households in terms of Autonomous Communities, size of locality, social class, and number of persons in household was selected. Second, Internet users older than 15 years of age within households were identified and selected.

For this study, we focused on data from 2701 Internet users who completed the online questionnaire. From these 2701 respondents with reported data, 1902 computers were scanned by iScan software and data from their computers were collected. For the analyses of responses to the online questionnaire, data from the 2701 respondents were used. For the analyses of the relationship between reported and scanned data, the subsample of 1902 participants was used. To better control for potentially biased responses, questions were randomly presented.

Materials

Reported data

Socio-demographic variables: Socio-demographic variables were: sex (male – 51.1%, female – 48.9%), age in years ($M = 39.53$, $SD = 12.75$), educational background (highest educational level attainment, from 1 – elementary to 3 – university studies, $M = 2.36$, $SD = 0.59$), and size of locality (from 1 less than 10,000 to 6 more than 500,000 inhabitants, $M = 3.75$, $SD = 1.79$).

Computer use risk perceptions and risk attitudes

Following the structure proposed by Weber, Blais, and Betz (2002), we measured computer use risk attitudes and risk perceptions across six new items. These six new items were created to measure respondents' risk perceptions and risk attitudes of several activities people might engage when using computers (1 = no risky to 7 = extremely risky) and, also, the probability that they would engage in those activities (1 = extremely unlikely to 7 = extremely likely). The six items measured activities such as to disable antivirus software to speed up computers, to download and open unrequested attached documents, not using antivirus software at all, to reveal bank account information through electronic mail, to accept unknown contacts in social networks, and to do online banking from public access computers. Averaged scale scores were computed for risk perceptions ($M = 5.40$, $SD = 1.19$) and risk attitudes ($M = 2.14$, $SD = 1.06$). Preliminary analyses showed that internal consistency for these scales was adequate ($.77 \geq$ Cronbach's $\alpha \leq .84$). Risk perceptions significantly correlated with recreational, social, and health/safety risk perceptions short scales of Domain-Specific Risk Taking Scale (Dospert) (Weber, Blais, and Betz 2002) and with the corresponding risk attitudes short scales. Likewise, computer use risk attitudes significantly correlated with the recreational, social, and health/safety

risk attitudes short scales. Computer use risk attitudes were positively and significantly related to recreational ($r = .194, p < .001$) and health/security ($r = .405, p < .001$) risk attitudes, and negatively related to social risk attitudes ($r = -.166, p < .001$). As for the risk perceptions, computer use risk perceptions were positively and significantly related to recreational ($r = .131, p < .001$) and health/security ($r = .294, p < .001$) risk perceptions and negatively related to social risk perceptions ($r = .255, p < .001$). Detailed information about the short version of Dospert is available from authors upon request.

General propensity to risk

The Brief Sensation Seeking Scale (Hoyle et al. 2002) is a four-item scale that measures trait sensation-seeking. Items responses ranged from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree ($M = 2.81, SD = 0.85$). Internal consistency for this scale was adequate (Cronbach's $\alpha = .77$).

Scanned data

We collected information about the existence of malicious software in respondents' computers through the use of iScan software. A total of 1902 computers were scanned. Computers were classified as not infected (40.1%) and infected (59.9%). Not infected computers were those computers with no malicious software in the scanning results, while infected computers presented some kind of malicious software. The variable Infected indicated the presence of malware in respondents' computers (0 = no, 1 = yes).

Data analyses

The analytical strategy was as follows. In the first stage, the measurement model of the 12 items of computer use risk perceptions and attitudes was analyzed. To do so, confirmatory factor analyses were carried out using Mplus software (Muthén and Muthén 1998–2010). In the second stage, the relationships between both sensation-seeking and computer use risk perceptions and attitudes and the presence of an infected computer were studied using Multivariate and Univariate Analyses of Variance. At this step, we analyzed if users with infected computers scored differently in both sensation-seeking and computer use risk perceptions and attitudes. Finally, in the third stage, we explored the role that sensation-seeking and computer use risk perceptions and attitudes had on the explanation of the presence of an infected computer. Structural equation modeling was used to analyze the relationships among sensation-seeking, both computer use risk perceptions and attitudes, and the presence of an infected computer. To correct for departures of multivariate kurtosis, the Satorra–Bentler chi-squared was used for computation of fit indexes. Chi-squared statistics, CFI, and RMSEA were used to assess model fit. Model fit was considered adequate if, at least, $CFI \geq .95$, and $RMSEA \leq .05$ with a 95% confidence interval (CI) (.00, .05). Likelihood-Ratio Tests were conducted between nested models for model selection.

Results

Computer use risk attitudes and risk perceptions

The measurement model of the 12 items of computer use risk perceptions and attitudes was analyzed using confirmatory factor analysis. Analyses were conducted in

a sequential fashion. The first model (Model 1) predicted two correlated factors (computer use risk perceptions and attitudes, respectively). In this model, no cross-loadings or correlated errors were allowed and the correlation between computer use risk perceptions and attitudes latent factors was freely estimated. This model poorly fitted the data: $\chi^2(53) = 2525.99, p < .001$, robust CFI = .79, RMSEA = .13, 95% CI (.13, .14). Inspection of the Lagrange Test results for correlated error terms revealed that the residual terms of items measuring both risk perceptions and attitudes of the same type of computer use (i.e. to disable antivirus software to speed up computers) needed to be freely estimated by the model. This circumstance usually appears in designs with repeated measures (see for instance, Herrero and Gracia 2007 for an example) where the sources of error of the same items across various time points need to be estimated.

In our case, given that the same behaviors were analyzed across various conditions (risk perception and risk attitudes), we might expect that sources of error needed also to be freely estimated by the model. Thus, in Model 2, five correlated errors were estimated. This model clearly increased model fit: $\chi^2(47) = 433.73, p < .001$, robust CFI = .97, RMSEA = .05, 95% CI (.05, .06). Close inspection of Lagrange Test results indicated that model fit could be improved if one correlated error was freely estimated. This correlated error corresponded to the following items of the risk perceptions factor: to accept unknown contacts in social networks and to do online banking from public access computers. This final measurement model (Model 3) showed an adequate fit to the data: $\chi^2(46) = 325.74, p < .001$, robust CFI = .98, RMSEA = .05, 95% CI (.04, .05). Likelihood-Ratio Test between nested models showed that Model 3 statistically fitted the data better than model 2 ($\Delta \chi^2(1) = 107.56, p < .001$). Standardized results for Model 3 are presented in Table 1.

Results from Table 1 indicate that all items loaded statistically significantly in their corresponding factors (p 's $< .001$). The estimated correlation among factors was negative and statistically significant ($r = -.56, p < .001$). The correlation between residual terms was statistically significant ($r = .18, p < .001$), suggesting that these two items shared common error variance.

Relationships among scanned data and self-reported data

Computer risk perceptions and risk attitudes, sensation-seeking, and scanned data about malicious software

We tested if domain-specific computer risk attitudes, risk perceptions, and sensation-seeking were related to the presence of malicious software in users' computer. To do so, a set multivariate analyses of variance (MANOVA) or univariate analyses of variance (ANOVA), when appropriate, were conducted. Univariate ANOVA followed MANOVA's to test for the mean differences for each variable. We checked the assumption that computer use risk attitudes and risk perceptions would be different across groups of infected computers. Also, we expected that the general measure of sensation-seeking would be different across groups of infected computers. Results indicated that computer use risk attitudes and risk perceptions scores were different across groups of infected computers (Wilk's $\lambda = .994, p < .01$). Univariate analyses are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Measurement model for risk perceptions and risk attitudes' items: standardized factor loadings ($N = 2701$).

Item	Risk Perceptions	Risk Attitudes
Not using antivirus at all	.821***	.660***
To disable antivirus software to speed up computers	.817***	.744***
To accept unknown contacts in social networks	.575***	.587***
To download and open unrequested attached documents	.743***	.657***
To reveal bank account information through electronic mail	.688***	.595***
To do online banking from public access computers	.472***	.449***

*** $p < .001$.

Results of Table 2 indicate that infected computers corresponded to respondents with higher levels of computer use risk attitudes ($F = 8.56, p = .003$) and lower levels of computer use risk perceptions ($F = 7.80, p = .005$). These infected computers, however, belonged to respondents with similar levels of the general trait of sensation-seeking ($F = 1.07, ns$).

Causal model

Using the technique of causal modeling, we analyzed whether the existence of an infected computer was predicted by the general trait of sensation-seeking, the computer use risk perceptions, and the computer use risk attitudes. Also, in this model, we tested for the effects of sensation-seeking on infected computers through its potential effect on the domain-specific computer use risk perceptions and risk attitudes. Finally, sex, age, and education were included in the model as covariates

Table 2. Means, standard deviations, and group differences on Internet risk attitudes and perceptions of infected and non-infected computers ($N = 1902$).

	Not infected	Infected	F	p
Computer use				
Risk attitudes			8.56	.003
M	2.02	2.15		
SD	(1.02)	(1.02)		
Risk perceptions			7.80	.005
M	5.53	5.38		
SD	(1.12)	(1.18)		

so the coefficients for the substantial part of the model were net of sex, age, and education effects. The model was estimated using Mplus software (Muthén and Muthén 1998–2010). Estimates among continuous latent factors are linear regression coefficients while estimates between continuous latent factors and the dependent categorical variable are logistic regression coefficients. This final model (Model 4) showed an adequate fit to the data: $\chi^2(46) = 475.07$, $p < .001$, robust CFI = .97, RMSEA = .04, 95% CI (.03, .04). Model 4 results are presented in Figure 1.

Results in Figure 1 indicate that higher scores on a general trait of sensation-seeking were related to the existence of malicious software in users' computers to the extent that this general trait translated into lower risk perceptions and higher risk attitudes. Thus, sensation-seekers lowered their risk perceptions which, in turn, increased their risk attitudes. These risk attitudes increased the likelihood of having malicious software in their computers. Moreover, the effect of sensation-seeking and risk perceptions on the existence of an infected computer was mediated by their effect on risk attitudes. In other words, sensation-seeking was statistically unrelated to the existence of an infected computer ($\beta = -.04$, ns), unless it was translated into computer use risk perceptions and risk attitudes. Only the computer use risk attitudes were statistically predictive ($\beta = .08$, $p < .05$) of the existence of an infected computer.

Discussion

Literature has traditionally shown the potentially harmful consequences of risk-taking in a variety of domains (Anderson and Brown 1984; Gerrard et al. 1996; Hammond and Horswill 2001; Llewellyn 2008; Zaleski 1984; Zuckerman 1974, 1983, 2007; Zuckerman and Kuhlman 2000; Zuckerman, Tushup, and Finner 1976). Less scholarly attention, however, has been directed to the study of risk-taking in the computer use domain. Using scanned data from 1901 computers, we sought to analyze the potentially harmful consequences that sensation-seeking and computer use risk perceptions and attitudes had on users' computer vulnerability. To do so,

Figure 1. Causal model for the role of sensation-seeking, computer risk perceptions, and attitudes on computer's harm ($N = 1902$).

computer use domain-specific measures of risk perception and risk attitudes were previously developed and their psychometric characteristics were analyzed using data from a national survey of 2901 Internet users. Next, using the causal modeling technique, we empirically analyzed the statistical influences that both general propensity to risk (i.e. sensation-seeking) and computer domain-specific risk perception and risk attitudes had on the existence of malicious malware in users' computer.

First, findings from our study indicated that the computer use risk attitudes and risk perceptions' scales showed adequate internal consistency. Also, scale scores in this domain (i.e. computer use) were significantly correlated to other domains. Computer use attitudes were positively related to recreational and health/security risk perceptions and negatively related to social risk attitudes. When analyzing computer use risk perceptions, the same tendency emerged: they were negatively related to social risk perceptions and positively related to recreational and health/security risk perceptions. The measure of general propensity to risk was also significantly related to computer use attitudes and perceptions. Thus, scoring on sensation-seeking was positively related to scores on computer use risk attitudes and negatively related to scores on computer use risk perceptions. Overall, these findings are consistent with both the theoretical explanations of risk-taking that emphasize its domain-specific aspects as well as with theories that put the accent on personality characteristics and predict that sensation-seekers would show greater risk attitudes and lower risk perceptions across domains. In our case, the computer use domain is not an exception to this prediction. Also, as several researchers have found, risk perceptions and risk attitudes might vary by content domain (Gerrard et al. 1996; Hammond and Horswill 2001; Llewellyn 2008; Mitchell et al. 2002) and an individual might show risk-taking tendencies in one domain but display more conservative behavior in another. Findings from our study suggest that respondents with more risk attitudes and risk perceptions in the social domain tend to be more conservative in the computer use domain. Further research should disentangle these empirical relationships.

Second, we tested if scale scores on risk attitudes and perceptions were predictive of the existence of malicious software in users' computer. In other words, we tested for the potentially harmful consequences that holding risk attitudes and risk perceptions would have on users' computer. Results showed that infected computers belonged to users with more positive risk attitudes and less risk perceptions in the computer use domain. We also tested if general propensity to risk predicted the presence of malicious software in users' computers. We could not find a statistical relationship between general propensity to risk and the presence of malicious software in users' computer. Although this result apparently challenged the available empirical evidence on the personal characteristics of risk-takers (Bromiley and Curley 1992; Eysenck and Eysenck 1977; Lejuez et al. 2002; Nicholson et al. 2005; Zuckerman 1974), the study of the indirect relationships between sensation-seeking and the presence of harmful consequences in users computers revealed that the influence of sensation-seeking was fully mediated by the existence of lower risk perceptions and higher risk attitudes. This finding is in accordance with the moderating effect of risk perception on risk behavior suggested by Sitkin and Pablo (1992). Thus, while risk attitudes and risk perceptions are key to understand risk-taking (Bechara 2004; Ersche et al. 2005; Weber 2001; Weber and Milliman 1997), more general propensity to risk, such as sensation-seeking, would play an important role in predicting the existence of such risk attitudes and risk perceptions across different situations. This would also support Weber and Milliman's (1997) claim that the

degree to which people find perceived risk attractive might remain stable across situations, probably as a function of a personal general propensity to risk. In our study, the general measure of sensation-seeking was predictive of both computer use risk perceptions and risk attitudes which in turn translated into the existence of malicious software in users' computers. This would further suggest that risk behaviors linked to lower risk attitudes and perceptions could be responsible for that.

While results of our study suggest that both the characteristics of the person (sensation-seeking) and the situation (computer use risk perceptions and attitudes) might have an influence on computer use risky behaviors, we should be cautious about the intentionality of these behaviors. Literature on the relationship between attitude and behavior has largely explored the potential role that intention to engage in a behavior might have on actual behaviors. For instance, expectancy value models of attitudes emphasize the influence of intention on behavior (Eagly and Chaiken 1998) while other theories such as attitudinal accessibility and automatic activation of attitudes do not (Fazio 1995) (see Gracia and Herrero 2006 for an analysis).

Expectancy value models, such as theories of planned (Ajzen 2011) and reasoned behavior (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975), have been extensively used in the study of risk-taking, creating the feeling that it could be described mostly in rational terms. Explanations focusing on the non-intentional aspects of computer risky behaviors, however, need also to be taken into account as it would probably give a more complete understanding of the relationships among risk perceptions, risk attitudes, and risk behavior. In this sense, Stanton et al. (2005) have shown that while intentionality is a key aspect of security behaviors most of the times (see also, D'Arcy, Hovav, and Galletta 2009; Shechtman and Dvir 2006), in some cases, the unintentional behavior may lead to computer risky behaviors. Lack of awareness of basic information security principles and the lack of ability to setup complex technology configurations may be regarded as examples of unintentional behaviors leading to risky computer-related behaviors. Further research focusing on both intentional and non-intentional computer use risk behaviors is warranted.

Strengths and limitations

Our study presents strengths and potential limitations. The innovative approach in measuring both self-reported and scanned data is among the more relevant strengths of the study. Although there is a widespread use of self-reported measures in online questionnaires (see Herrero and Meneses 2006 for an analysis of its limitations), the study took a quite different approach in measuring the potentially harmful consequences in users' computers. Upon approval of respondents, almost 2000 computers were remotely scanned in search of malicious software, up-to-date operative systems, and other security threats. Combining self-reported and objective information might add generalizability to the study findings. The large data-set used in the analyses as well as the adequate psychometric properties of the measures used should also add consistency to the study findings.

The study presents also potential limitations. First, in addition to risk perceptions affecting behavior, risk-taking behavior might influence the use of strategies to minimize their perceptions of risk. Longitudinal (Gerrard et al. 1996) research has suggested that more frequent risk-takers actually show lower personal risk perceptions. Study designs that include panel or longitudinal data could clarify the directionality of the hypothesis: attitudes affecting behavior or the reverse. Second, the study did

not directly measure risk behaviors so we cannot conclude that general propensity to risk, risk attitudes, and risk perceptions translated into actual risk behaviors. This limitation notwithstanding, the approach followed in our research consisted in detecting computer malicious software through remote scanning of equipment. The presence of malicious software could be considered a negative consequence of the existence of potential risk behaviors. Note here that self-reported risk behaviors might have been affected by biased responding (i.e. socially desirable responding) and this had translated into a potential limitation to the study. With the use of more objective measures such as the remote scanning approach used in the study, we could overcome this potential limitation. Further research combining different measures of risk behaviors and their potentially harmful consequences should add generalizability to the study findings.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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